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Research Article

**AN ASSESSMENT OF THE CITRUS (GRAPEFRUIT) PARADISI
ANTIMICROBIAL EFFECTIVENESS VERSUS GENERAL
PATHOGENS THROUGH AGAR CULTURING**¹Dr Wazir Muhammad Hasan, ²Dr. Shanaza Khawar, ³Dr. Ramsha Luqman¹Medical Officer Civil Hospital Thowar Roundu Skardu²Central Park Medical College, Lahore³Mayo Hospital Lahore**Abstract**

Objectives: *Citrus paradisi* grape fruit's antimicrobial action versus general pathogens was assess in this study. *Staphylococcus aureus* establishing grape-similar bunches on agar culture is an explicit coccus.

Methodology: The research was completed at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from February to December 2017. Two variants of dilutions (50 mg extract/1ml DMSO and 25 mg extract/1ml DMSO) was used for the formulation of extract. With the help of various absorptions of the ready excerpts, antibacterial activities were resolute. Mueller Hinton agar plates were cautiously immunized using a bacterial spread of 10 µl and then plates were label accurately. With the help of plain tongs, discs adjusted on agar plates. 20 µl of the ready excerpt (50 mg extract/1ml DMSO dilution) affixed to discs of half of the plates, whereas 10 µl of all excerpt affixed to the left-over plates' discs. After that these plates gestated for 1 day at 37°C. Also, 25 mg extract/1ml DMSO was undergoing through a similar process. **Results:** Label all the excerpts used for *Bacillus Cereus* as CF-04, CF-12, CF-13 and CF-14. In CF-14, maximum shyness was noticed with respect to remaining parts which show the effectivity of ciprofloxacin in this group. **Discussion:** We assessed the antimicrobial and antioxidant potential of various parts of *citrus paradisi* plant's excerpts concocted in a solution of ethyl acetate. A current research study showed the antimicrobial impacts of various sections of grapefruit plant versus 06 general bacterial sprains and extremely affirmative region of hang-ups were perceive. **Conclusion:** CF-10 exhibited most positive inhibition zone out of all prepared extracts. CF-02, CF-04, CF-10 and CF-14 made from pulp, peel, leaves and stem of *citrus paradisi* respectively and were the ready excerpts used for *K pneumonia* and out of these excerpts, CF-14 revealed high inhibition zone.

Keywords: *K Pneumonia, Citrus, Paradisi, Antimicrobial, Pathogens and Variants.*

Corresponding author:**Dr. Wazir Muhammad Hasan,**

Medical Officer Civil Hospital Thowar Roundu, Skardu.

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INTRODUCTION:

Citrus Paradisi is associated with genre 'citrus', having an association with Rutaceae plants family. Grapefruit is also one of the famous fruits associated with Rutaceae plants family. It is a well-known citrus fruit which has an outer yellow skin and a ripened, thick and sour mash. The tree of grapefruit is also larger as compared to more citrus fruit plants, can be lengthened from 43 to 50 feet in height with an average of about 16 to 20 feet. Though the skin of the fruit is yellow, however, some fruits are having a pinkish peel. Its mash is sour and its colour differs from yellowish-white to dark or light pink [1].

Overall, citrus Paradisi fruits are considered to be health-giving. Citrus paradisi grapefruit consists of a productive vitamin C supply [2]. The taste of grapefruit has profuse, intricate pectin fibre [3] and its pink hue is prolific infamous effective anti-oxidant 'lycopene' [4]. Lycopene is a familiar defensive means for prostatic cancers and holds a probable capability to decrease the tumour cells progress [5]. Study on the advantages of citrus paradisi grapefruit juice recognized that the extracts of the grapefruit juice decrease the plasma cholesterol levels in numerous patients [6]. As the seeds also hold some quantity of antioxidants, these are also important [7]. The extract of seeds of citrus paradisi grapefruit, with known action versus both fungi and bacteria, has believed as a beneficial antimicrobial agent.

More vitamin C content in citrus paradisi grapefruits employs convincing antioxidant outcomes on human metabolism and has recorded the increased quicker improvement number of bacteria and viruses caused by common cold [8]. About 30% reduction has highlighted in breast cancer risk in post-menopausal women in a study organized in 2007. This advantage perceived to be because of hang-up of hepatic P-450 enzyme CYP3A4, which is accountable for metabolizing estrogen [9]. Citrus paradisi grapefruits have ample β carotenes, natural and powerful antioxidants versus growth of macular degeneration and GIT cancers [10]. Citrus paradisi' anti-inflammatory behaves have been a credit to the existence of flavanones, which lessen the level of blood cholesterol, resulting in a decrease in the growth of coronary artery diseases [11].

Because of massive usage of several antimicrobial drugs nowadays, there was a growing opposition of general bacteria to antibiotics. In current days, there has a cumulative opposition of ordinary bacteria to antibiotics, because of numeral antimicrobial drugs, owed to inherent competence of obtaining opposition to said drugs by means of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria.

It fetches the notice to antimicrobial characteristics of excerpts of the plant which contains bioactive

ingredients, can possibly kill the bacteria. Some famous and effective in bacterial killing phytochemicals include polyphenols, carotenoids, tannins and anthocyanin. Phytochemicals are influential plant-derived elements which aid to avoid chronic diseases in humans [12].

METHODOLOGY:

Extracts preparation: Two variants of dilutions (50 mg extract/1ml DMSO and 25 mg extract/1ml DMSO) was used for the formulation of extract. Grapefruit extracts were arranged through freshly collected 700 grams of the pulp of grapefruit plummeting in a glass vessel in 1000 ml of ethyl alcohol. In another vessel, separately dipped the peel powders, stem and dried leaf in 1000 ml of ethyl alcohol. All suspensions were keenly filtered through Whatman's paper filter, gradually evaporated the ethyl alcohol at room temperature by rotary evaporators at 90 rpm, and retained in the isolated vessel. Deposits were then gathered into Pyrex falcon tubes.

Specific media preparation: In this research study, for bacteria, growth medium of Mueller Hinton was used. This medium needs meat infusions, agar, starch and casein acid hydrolysate solution.

Bacterial strains growth: For the development of Salmonella typhi, E. Coli and Staphylococcus aureus, newly make MacConkey's agar was used, whereas EMB agar was used for progression of Bacillus cereus, Klebsiella pneumonia and Pseudomonas aeruginosa.

DMSO solution preparation: All extracts (25 mg) were cautiously measure on electric balance and then pour into Eppendorf glass tubes, and 1ml of DMSO was included in each glass tube, till obtainment of homogenous combination, put on vibrating vortex. In this study, DMSO was used as a negative control.

Disc Diffusion technique for extracts' anti-bacterial activities: In a specific growing medium, this method is used for testing the various bacteria's sensitivity and perceived the resilient to a particular antibiotic. With the usage of various extracted concentration, antibacterial activities were observed. Mueller Hinton agar plates were properly labelled after wary immunization with 10 μ l of bacterial spread. With plain tongs, the discs were placed on to agar plates. Twenty μ l of the ready excerpt (50 mg extract/1ml DMSO dilution) affixed to discs of half of the plates, whereas 10 μ l of all excerpt affixed to the leftover plates' discs. After that these plates gestated for 1 day at 37°C. Also, 25 mg extract/1ml DMSO was undergoing through a similar process.

Prepared extracts anti-bacterial activity using agar well-diffusion method: Mueller Hinton agar plates were

cautiously immunized using a bacterial wipe of 10 µl on whole culture plates. Wells were punched into the agar through a wooden cork, sterile and 10 µl of plant excerpts (50 mg/DMSO 1ml dilution) supplemented into wells, and 20 µl excerpts (50 mg/DMSO 1 ml dilution) was supplemented in the others half plates well. After that, for 1 day these plates were placed at 37°C in an incubator. Alkaline reagent, Froth, Keller Killians, Molish, Ninhydrin and Salkowski biochemical tests were employed for discovering active phytochemicals in plant excerpts.

RESULTS:

Label all the excerpts used for Bacillus Cereus as CF-04, CF-12, CF-13 and CF-14. In CF-14, maximum shyness was noticed with respect to remaining parts which show the effectivity of ciprofloxacin in this group. CF-04, CF-

12, CF-13 and CF-14 extracts were used against E. Coli and CF-12 was notice to be showing the most inhibition to ciprofloxacin with respect to remaining parts of that group. CF-04, CF-12, CF-13 and CF-14 excerpts used for Klebsiella pneumonia and CF-14 was noticed to be showing the most inhibition with respect to other sections which display the effectiveness of ciprofloxacin in that culture. Similarly, the excerpts used versus Pseudomonas aeruginosa were marked as CF-04, CF-12, CF-13 and CF-14. In CF-12 highest hang-up was observed with a comparison to other sections, presenting the useful action of ciprofloxacin in this group. Excerpts used for Bacillus Cereus were marked as CF-04, CF-12, CF-13 and CF-14. Most inhibition was observed in CF-14 with respect to remaining sections. It displays the effectiveness of ciprofloxacin in this culture.

Table – I: the Anti-bacterial activity of prepared citrus paradise extracts

Bacterial strains 10 µl	Prepared extracts 20 µl extracts		CF-4	CF-12	CF-13	CF-14
	Positive Control (mm)	Negative Control (mm)				
Staph aureus	30.00	0.00	18.00	26.00	28.00	30.00
Salmonella typhi	20.00	0.00	14.00	28.00	30.00	32.00
Bacillus cereus	18.00	0.00	12.00	18.00	12.00	18.00
E coli	20.00	0.00	14.00	26.00	22.00	28.00
P aeruginosa	2.00	0.00	20.00	32.00	34.00	36.00
K pneumonia	20.00	0.00	18.00	30.00	26.00	34.00

Bacterial strain (10 µl)	Extracts					
	25mg/l mL DMSO with 10 µl extract					
	Positive control (mm)	Negative control (mm)	GF 02	GF 06	GFIO	GF14
S. aureus	35.00	0.00	20.00	30.00	25.00	32.00
S ty phi	21.00	0.00	16.00	30.00	32.00	37.00
B. cereus	20.00	0.00	11.00	14.00	16.00	14.00
E. coli	21.00	0.00	11.00	27.00	20.00	25.00
P. aeruginosa	0.00	0.00	21.00	38.00	32.00	37.00
K. pneumonia	21.00	0.00	19.00	31.00	28.00	36.00

Bacterial strain (10 µl)	Extracts					
	25mg/1 mL DMSO with 10 µl extract					
	Positive control (mm)	Negative control (mm)	GF 02	GF 06	GF10	GF14
S. typhi	21.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.00	13.00
B. cereus	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	16.00	9.00
E. coli	21.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.00	11.00
P. aeruginosa	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
K. pneumonia	21.00	0.00	0.00	14.00	8.00	11.00

DISCUSSION:

For health full lifestyles it is required to regularly consume grapefruit. Citrus paradisi grapefruit is useful for health because of ample ascorbic acid (vitamin C) substance, it possesses minimum calories and it has profuse dietary fibres and potassium [18]. In this research study, we evaluated the antimicrobial and antioxidant capacity of excerpts of citrus paradisi plant various sections formulated in a solution of ethyl acetate. This research study verified the antimicrobial outcomes of grapefruit plant parts versus six general bacterial strains and observe a highly positive inhibitions region. In another study directed on the grapefruit seed excerpts' antimicrobial effects recognized that sanitized extracts of grapefruit seed revealed efficient antibacterial action in contradiction of both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. Extracts of this seed were having no side effect against human tissues and are effective in killing the bacteria through breaching into the cell wall mechanisms and

releasing the bacteria's cytoplasmic substances, yet at weak intensities of excerpts of the seed [19]. Extracts of the seed of grapefruit expressively lessened the recurrence of human pathogens like Salmonella typhi [20].

CONCLUSION:

Generally, this study draws attention to antimicrobial agents' existence in various sections of the plant of grapefruit, which can be efficiently utilized in a number of antibiotics in favour of inhibition of acute and chronic bacterial diseases. More research is required for proving the effectivity of these antimicrobial actions at the clinical phase.

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